

Harmony Between Reason and Faith

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Was the ideological project of harmonising reason and faith in the 16th century not destined to be provisional, that is, only a calming or balancing tool that, after fulfilling its purpose, could no longer have any reason to exist? Just as neoliberalism intended to be an escape route from the dictatorial violence of the 20th century (Harvey). As such, neoliberalism was conceived as a raft that allowed us to abandon the sinking ship of society and take us to solid ground, but after reaching the shore, it was clear that we had to abandon the raft and continue the journey. However, society set off on land without discarding the raft. In the 17th century, Bacon also panicked and was swept up in a scientific frenzy.

The ideological current that sought to pacify the radicalism of faith and the diminishing of reason in the 16th century, which was only meant to balance reason with faith and then disappear, has remained in our minds and has even managed to create an opposite imbalance, now radicalising scientific reason. This reversal of the Counter-Reformation is the philosophical issue of our time, and it is what ties us to the 16th century in a special way.

We are immersed in a hyper-scientific dictatorship. At present, science despises the idea of the soul. It is not only about denying its existence but about combating with extreme violence any attempt to prove that the soul exists. Yet, with its hatred of the soul (of metaphysics), science becomes, for that very reason, the great proof of its existence (this is Heidegger's thesis in *What is Metaphysics*). Heidegger says: when science claims that it will focus only on the world and nothing else, in that very assertion it is confirming the existence of nothingness. It is true that it asserts it will ignore it, that it will not pay attention to it because it is nothing, but it treats it as a subject of reference, thus giving us the essential and also the only proof we have to affirm it.

The prevailing dogma is clearly the scientific worldview. Only scientific research holds value. A metaphysical attempt to approach the truth is considered academically inappropriate and poor, thus suffering strong discredit. And this has happened under the auspices of all the philosophy and humanities departments in the faculties. They have not resisted the scientific coup d'état; they have fallen into the trap of conversion: like the Mesoamericans in the 16th century, when colonisation made them believe that to be free, they themselves had to want to be colonised and Christianised. Like an Indian convincing himself through an invisible external force that he is like a child, he has accepted being led by science down the path of truth. Science has made an entire academic department believe that a philosophically free system, that is, a true one, cannot exist outside the

scientific method. As Subirats says about conversion, it was the Indian who had to want to convert, and now it is the academic philosophy professor who must want to convert to scientism.

We have already pointed out above the miserable situation in which philosophy finds itself within the Academy. Many philosophers try to solve small interpretive problems in many micro-parcels of the system of knowledge; they elucidate contradictions and contrast every word through the external control of linguistic sub-specialists who each know, in turn, about a specific word. And each one in the study, looking at their own screen, without raising their head. Meanwhile, science keeps watch to ensure no one is distracted by the flight of flies. Naive philosophers all, they happily water their tiny discoveries in their private garden. Science funds them (Nietzsche) with a licence to have exclusive exploitation of their piece of cathedral wood. They have learned to chatter, but no one dares to raise their head to ask what is happening with philosophy. What has happened to it in this last century? And how have we been so naive and innocent to trust such a twisted and criminal power? Does no one care about this historical betrayal of science to metaphysics? Now, after the destruction, philosophy is an empty continent (Subirats). Science ideologically claims that there was never a philosophical culture as such before, or that if it did exist, it was always insubstantial and meaningless, lacking maturity, a culture in any case childish and immature. It has thus left us without essence, without the capacity to be, and has imprinted its spirit upon us, as if it were about fulfilling a need. Maintaining the borders of philosophy, its limits, the contour that bounded its kingdom, is in itself what logically allowed it to fill a void. Without the existence of those borders, there would be no gap to fill. That is why we must aim at those old walls of ours and bring them down so that science loses its control of the territory. So that it stops taking advantage of us.

This is the way to balance or harmonise once again two historical forces that today take the form of science and metaphysics: we must rescue our first and oldest philosophical formula: the risk of being wise is borne by others, not by the philosopher. Therefore, we must begin by denying our identity as scientific philosophers, that is, as intellectuals who believe they know the truth. The classical sense of a philosopher defines the character of the intellectual who distances themselves from the belief that they possess any decisive knowledge. Only the scientist takes that risk. Science pushes philosophical society to assume that risk (Ulrich Beck), but it is an impoverishing danger for philosophical souls. Just as in neoliberalism the pursuit of wealth almost always turns the poor into someone even poorer (economic exile of the 21st century), in the scientific system the pursuit of truth turns the philosopher into someone poorer than before in terms of truth. In scientism, only the scientist is rich; there is only one favourable or positive category of

being. To be a philosopher in a scientific system means to be poor, so to claim to be a philosopher of science is to further impoverish our soul and our condition.

It is better suited for a philosophical revolution that seeks the reevaluation of philosophical reality (of its classical branches: logic, metaphysics, politics, and ethics).

And just as no one wants to accept that they are mad, no one willingly accepts that they are poor. But as Socrates says, to be truly philosophical means to accept that we are poor in knowledge. Poor in general. No one wants to recognise that they are poor. Compulsive appearance (conversion) is our distinctive trait as a historical subject. Philosophy should fight for these ideas so dear to us of 'critique' and not exhaust or betray itself by allowing that giant which promised to carry us on its shoulders to drag us along the ground as it advances. At first, it carried us like a donkey, and we bore its essences on our back while it crossed the mountains of knowledge. And now that it no longer needs us to carry anything, it repays us by mocking us, dragging us, and torturing us.

And no one says a word, nor is there any Jango or Quixote in these Spanish lands to restore the grace of life to us."